

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added Course 2021-22 academic year for BPT

HOSPITAL ADMINISTRATION

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

VALUE ADDED COURSE ON
HOSPITAL ADMINISTRATION
FOR BPT (2019 BATCH)
15 weeks (30 hours)

Course Objectives

1. To provide an understanding of the functions of management and administration of the healthcare.
2. To teach leadership and managerial skills that will positively affect performance as a healthcare manager.

CONTACT
0824-2429139

FOR MORE DETAILS :
deanphysiotherapy@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

Course period	From June till September 2022, during 6 th semester (15 weeks)
Duration	30 hours (2 hours/week)
Language of instruction	English
Participants	BPT 3 rd year undergraduates (2019 batch)

Course Objectives:

1. To provide an understanding of the functions of management and administration of the healthcare.
2. To teach leadership and managerial skills that will positively affect performance as a healthcare manager.

Module 1

Introduction: Branches of administration, Nature and scope of administration, How to be an effective administrator, Planning hospital administration as part of a balanced health care program, Principles of hospital administration and its applications to physiotherapy.

4 hours

Module 2

Planning and organization: Planning cycle, Principles of organizational charts, Resource and quality management, planning change –innovation; Financial issues including budget and income generation.

5 hours

Module 3

Hospital administration: Organization, Staffing, Information, Communication, Coordination, Cost of services, Monitoring and evaluation; National health policy and health care system in India.

5 Hours

Module 4

Organization of physiotherapy department: Planning, Space, Manpower, Other basic resources; organizing meetings, committees, and negotiations.

4 Hours

Module 5

Personnel management: Personnel performance appraisal system, Quality care delivery from the staff.

Material management: Pharmacy, Hospital waste disposal.

Quality assurance: Hospital acquired infection; Quality assurance through record review and medical audit; Public relations in hospital and human resource management.

12 Hours

Attendance Policy:

The course requires compulsory 75% attendance and only in this case a student will be issued a certificate.

References:

1. Gupta J. D. Hospital Administration and Management- a comprehensive guide. 2nd ed. Jaypee Brothers, 2015.
2. Joshi D. C, Joshi M. Hospital Administration. Jaypee Brothers, 2017.
3. Francis C M. Hospital Administration. 3rd ed. Jaypee Brothers, 2004.
4. Davies, R and Macaulay. Hospital Planning and Administration, BMC.

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

ABHAYASREE M (5SU19PT002)

for completing the 15 week value added
course on "Hospital Administration" from
June till September 2022

Dr. Annayya Kulal Ulthoor
Course Instructor

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

ADITHYA M (5SU19PT003)

for completing the 15 week value added
course on "Hospital Administration" from
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Dr. Annayya Kulal Ulthoor
Course Instructor

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

AHAMMED NASEEH V B (5SU19PT004)

for completing the 15 week value added
course on "Hospital Administration" from
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Dr. Annayya Kulal Ulthoor
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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

AISHWARYA BIJUSH (5SU19PT005)

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

ALBIN JACOB VARUGHESE (5SU19PT006)

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

ANAMIKA K (5SU19PT007)

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

ANJANA MANOJ (5SU19PT008)

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

ANJANA MOHAN (5SU19PT009)

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This Certificate is presented to

ANJIMA K V (5SU19PT010)

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

ATHIRA P KRISHNA (5SU19PT011)

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

AYESHA SAFEERA (5SU19PT012)

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

AYSHA FARHA (5SU19PT013)

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BAGHELE AISHWARYA RAJESH (5SU19PT014)

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BENECIA ANITA CARDOZO (5SU19PT015)

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This Certificate is presented to

BHAVYASHREE C VAIDYA (5SU19PT016)

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This Certificate is presented to

CHANNAMMA R NELAGUDDA (5SU19PT017)

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CHARAN JITENDRA VAIDYA (5SU19PT018)

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CHAUHAN KAVITA BABURAM (5SU19PT019)

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This Certificate is presented to

DANY ELDHOSE (5SU19PT020)

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This Certificate is presented to

DEEPTHI K J (5SU19PT021)

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This Certificate is presented to

DI – ANN VERA VAZ (5SU19PT022)

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This Certificate is presented to

DIAS RICHA CHRISTINE (5SU19PT023)

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

FARSANA T (5SU19PT024)

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This Certificate is presented to

FATHIMA (5SU19PT025)

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This Certificate is presented to

FATHIMA ARSANA (5SU19PT026)

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FINU ANTONY (5SU19PT028)

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GIFIN M PAUL (5SU19PT029)

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GOKUL A P (5SU19PT030)

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This Certificate is presented to

GREESHMA M EDWIN (5SU19PT031)

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This Certificate is presented to

HARSHITHA G S (5SU19PT032)

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HAZEBA FATHIMA (5SU19PT033)

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This Certificate is presented to

HEMANTH A V (5SU19PT034)

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HRUTHIKA M (5SU19PT035)

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IFTHISHAM (5SU19PT036)

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This Certificate is presented to

JANE CARYN LOBO (5SU19PT037)

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JILSHA P Y (5SU19PT038)

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JITHIN T (5SU19PT039)

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This Certificate is presented to

JOYCE MARIAM JOSY (5SU19PT040)

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course on "Hospital Administration" from
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This Certificate is presented to

KARUNA VISHRAM PARAB (5SU19PT041)

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This Certificate is presented to

KRISHNAPRIYA BIJU (5SU19PT042)

for completing the 15 week value added
course on "Hospital Administration" from
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Dr. Annayya Kulal Ulthoor
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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

LUGELLE MARIA DE GRACA FERNANDES (5SU19PT043)

for completing the 15 week value added
course on "Hospital Administration" from
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Dr. Annayya Kulal Ulthoor
Course Instructor

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

MEHTAB JUBAPU SHUAIB (5SU19PT045)

for completing the 15 week value added
course on "Hospital Administration" from
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Dr. Annayya Kulal Ulthoor
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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

MOHAMMED TAHA (5SU19PT046)

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course on "Hospital Administration" from
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Dr. Annayya Kulal Ulthoor
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This Certificate is presented to

MUHAMMED RASIL P M (5SU19PT047)

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

MUHAMMED SINAN K (5SU19PT049)

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course on "Hospital Administration" from
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Dr. Annayya Kulal Ulthoor
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Certificate of Completion

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MUHAMMED SHANID P (5SU19PT050)

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This Certificate is presented to

MUHSIN K.P (5SU19PT051)

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course on "Hospital Administration" from
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Dr. Annayya Kulal Ulthoor
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NEELINA K (5SU19PT052)

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NIRMAL JAIN (5SU19PT053)

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PEARL ASTIDA D'SA (5SU19PT054)

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This Certificate is presented to

PUSHPA N NAYAK (5SU19PT056)

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RAGHAVENDRA A N (5SU19PT057)

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This Certificate is presented to

RATHIKA RAVINDRA NAYAK (5SU19PT059)

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This Certificate is presented to

RAVI R H (5SU19PT060)

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This Certificate is presented to

REMYA RAVEENDRAN (5SU19PT061)

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SAIDH ALI HAMZA (5SU19PT064)

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This Certificate is presented to

SANDRA K R (5SU19PT065)

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SANGAR SHIVANI NAVIN (5SU19PT066)

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This Certificate is presented to

SANGEETH SANTHOSH (5SU19PT067)

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This Certificate is presented to

SAYED FARZANA PARVEEN (5SU19PT068)

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

SEBINNABI TORGAL (5SU19PT069)

for completing the 15 week value added
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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

SHAHISTA BANU (5SU19PT070)

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This Certificate is presented to

SHAIKH SUMERA MEHEK NASEEM IRFAN (5SU19PT071)

for completing the 15 week value added
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SHIFANA M E (5SU19PT073)

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SHRAMIKA (5SU19PT074)

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SHRIRAKSHA R ANGADI (5SU19PT075)

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STACY SANTAN FERNANDES (5SU19PT076)

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

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for completing the 15 week value added
course on "Hospital Administration" from
June till September 2022

Dr. Annayya Kulal Ulthoor
Course Instructor

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Dean

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